

Digital Geopolitics of BRICS: Cooperation Strategies in Artificial Intelligence and Data Security for Inclusive Multilateralism

Tuboi Bernardo Chaúque

Abstract

This presentation addresses how Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a central tool of power in modern geopolitics and how the BRICS+ bloc acts to ensure that technological development benefits the Global South. The focus is on equitable governance, data security, cooperation challenges among member countries, and the pursuit of digital sovereignty, especially from the Brazilian perspective.

Keywords: Geopolitics; Governance; Sovereignty; BRICS+

Introduction

Artificial intelligence(AI), which originated in the 1950s after World War II, has become an alternative tool for automating mechanical and intellectual tasks based on advanced and modern technologies in various areas such as manufacturing, engineering, transportation, healthcare, and more strategic areas such as cybersecurity and the military arena. Thus, its strategic use has become a representation of power and domination.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as one of the most transformative technologies of the 21st century, with disruptive potential that spans virtually every sector of human activity.(Soares 2025)

This race for automation, and consequently the race for dominance, enters the current geopolitical scenario in reconfiguration as a differential in terms of power, thus creating a new dispute, the dispute for cyberspace and data control, representing two classes, the dominant (which controls these tools) and the dominated (devoid of these tools or underdeveloped).

In this new global geopolitics, characterized by the end of US hegemony, the rise of China as a superpower, the strengthening of counter-hegemonic blocs, the case of BRICS+, the war in the Middle East, and the return to the nuclear and technological arms race. BRICS+ is an important actor in this new global geopolitics, especially from the perspective of countering North-South geopolitical domination.

BRICS+ as an emerging and counter-hegemonic economic bloc is an important player in this new reconfiguration of global geopolitics, and internal preparation and cooperation can make all the difference. First, we must view BRICS+ not simply as a bloc, but as a strategic bridge between emerging economies and the geopolitical South.

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According to BRICS “Artificial Intelligence represents a milestone opportunity to boost development towards a more equitable future, fostering innovation, enhancing productivity, advancing sustainable practices, and concretely improving the lives of people everywhere on the planet.”

According to the BRICS Leaders’ Statement on the Global Governance of Artificial Intelligence, the bloc sees Artificial Intelligence as a historic opportunity to drive development toward a more equitable future, promoting innovation, increasing productivity,

advancing sustainable practices, and tangibly improving the lives of people across the globe.

The BRICS AI governance declaration establishes comprehensive guidelines for responsible artificial intelligence development, emphasizing UN-led frameworks, digital sovereignty, and inclusive global governance that prioritizes developing nations' participation in AI policy-making. (NEMKO DIGITAL, 2025)

(BRAZIL, 2024) We recognise the huge potential of ICTs bridging the digital divides for socioeconomic growth and development. We also acknowledge challenges and threats stemming from and within the digital realm.

In paragraph 54 of the BRICS Summit Declaration in Kazan, Russia, the introduction to the topic of digital technology was characterized by recognition of the potential that digital tools have to drive socioeconomic development and reduce digital disparities, without ignoring the challenges and threats that come with them.

There is also a cautious recommendation regarding their use, recommending a more strategic application and the formulation of shared regulations to ensure the interoperability of trade and supply chains, as well as a vision of more ethical use with a focus on internal security and state sovereignty, warning that cyberspace must be protected, as it constitutes digital frontiers.

We express serious concern over exponential spread and proliferation of disinformation, misinformation, including propagating false narratives and fake news, as well as hate speech especially on digital platforms fueling radicalization and conflicts. (BRAZIL, 2024)

In paragraph 56 of the BRICS Summit Declaration in Kazan, Russia the central concern is the growing use of digital spaces to proliferate misinformation and hate speech, meaning that digital spaces have become promoters, radicalizers, and reproducers of conflicts and discriminatory stereotypes. Digital literacy is thus proposed as a strategy to overcome these evils.

Held under the theme “Strengthening Global South Cooperation for More Inclusive and Sustainable Governance,” the 17th BRICS Summit took place in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, on July 6-7, 2025. The Brazilian Presidency of BRICS brought with it a very dynamic energy to the bloc and focused on AI governance as a priority, producing a specific document on global AI governance, thus signifying that advances are not being ignored and that the bloc seeks to expand its digital presence in this new geopolitical landscape.

“We recognize that Artificial Intelligence (AI) represents a unique opportunity to drive development towards a more prosperous future. To achieve that goal, we underscore that global governance of AI should mitigate potential risks and address the needs of all countries, including those of the Global South. A collective global effort is needed to establish an AI governance that upholds our shared values, addresses risks, builds trust, and ensures broad and inclusive international collaboration and access, in accordance with sovereign laws, including capacity building for developing countries, with the United Nations at its core.” (Brazil, 2025).

This initial statement, in paragraph 16 of the BRICS Summit Declaration in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, shows that the BRICS Digitalization agenda is a priority and a strategy to foster the development of the countries in the bloc. Global AI Governance in BRICS has a more cautious approach, from a more inclusive perspective, especially for countries in the Global South, and seeks to maintain shared values that ensure collaboration based on trust and respect for the sovereignty of member countries, meaning that strategies are subject to local laws for their implementation.

The bloc sees the strengthening of global governance in AI as a mechanism for reducing structural digital asymmetries within the digital universe, seeking to position itself to face this threat of digital domination, or simply technological colonization, since colonization is characterized by domination and dependence.

Strategies

Given these opportunities and threats, strategy becomes paramount. We look forward to BRICS cooperation to help developing countries strengthen AI capacity building. Paragraph 78 of the BRICS Summit Declaration in Kazan, Russia reinforces the idea of discussion and active leadership on the topic of artificial intelligence, seeking other international actors, with the United Nations playing an important role in regulatory terms. The challenge remains for deeper cooperation among BRICS+ member countries in the area of AI and their own regulations.

Recognising that the rapid technological change, including the rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence has the potential to bring new opportunities for socioeconomic development around the globe, we encourage more international discussions, we support the United Nations to play an important role in global AI governance and welcome the UN General Assembly resolution A/RES/78/311 entitled Enhancing International Cooperation on Capacity-Building of Artificial Intelligence, which was adopted by consensus. (Brazil, 2024)

The bloc has been seeking to expand this technological autonomy in strategic areas such as the digital industry, digital economy, and academia through training programs and experience sharing. China's more active leadership in this process and Brazil's cooperation also stand out. We see this in paragraph 57 of the BRICS Leaders' Declaration – Rio de Janeiro 2025.

'We acknowledge that under the Brazilian Chairship, the BRICS Artificial Intelligence High-Level Forum, co-hosted by China and organized by China-BRICS Artificial Intelligence Development and Cooperation Center, has been held in Brasilia during the 9th BRICS Industry Ministers Meeting.' (Brazil 2024)

According to the leaders, a collective global effort is needed to establish AI governance that represents our shared values, mitigates risks, builds trust, and ensures broad and inclusive

international collaboration and access, including capacity building for developing countries, with the United Nations at the center. Showed at the paragraph 78 of the BRICS Summit Declaration in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

We reaffirm that the ultimate purpose of BRICS cooperation in STI (Technology and Innovation) is to forge new productive forces for development of BRICS countries and advance sustainable development in its three dimensions, through a partnership rooted in collaboration, contributing to the strengthening of friendship, mutual understanding, and peaceful relations among BRICS nations (Brazil, 2025).

Challenges

According to (Felisberto, 2025), one of the major challenges for cooperation in the field of AI among the BRICS countries stems from technological asymmetries and data processing models. For example, Brazil has more principled strategies, such as the LGPD (General Data Protection Law), which focuses more on conveying trust and transparency, in contrast to the Chinese model, which is more statist and controlling, where AIs the digital domain are used to maintain state order, from social stability to its application in the military. Finally, we have the Indian model, which is more constructive and infrastructural, prioritizing the construction of public digital infrastructures that positively affect the economy, strategically positioning itself in the commercial arena.

Data Security for Inclusive Multilateralism

Effectinace must be accompanied by a set of factors and elements that ensure inclusive, efficient, and reliable governance that does not compromise the sovereignty of states. We see this in paragraph 66 of the BRICS Leaders' Declaration – Rio de Janeiro 2025

Recognizing the central role of data to modern life as a catalyst for innovation-driven development and the formulation of informed and inclusive public policies, we reaffirm the need for a common and principle-based interoperable framework on data governance, including respect for national data sovereignty, efficient, convenient, safe and mutually agreed cross-border data flows and ethical use of data, to address the principles of collection, recording, storage, organization, processing and transfer of data; protect personal information rights and interests, including individual privacy; promote the interoperability of national data policy regulations; and distribute the monetary and non-monetary benefits of data among developing countries and their citizens.

Brazil's Digital Sovereignty in BRICS+, Limits of Cooperation, Strategic Internal Digital Governance

Digital sovereignty can be understood as a state's ability to autonomously control its digital infrastructure, data flows, critical services, and technological decision-making processes. Brazil faces significant challenges in maintaining its digital sovereignty, but it also has a relevant set of capabilities and accumulated experience. (Borba; Siqueira, 2025)

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